

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11607815>

THE REQUIREMENTS FOR THE MODERN TEACHING PROCESS

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ABSTRACT

School is an educational institution that determines the pedagogical basis of student activity. It requires students to develop high knowledge, skills, and abilities, show high results, and fully fulfill the requirements of DTS. Establishing a modern teaching process determines the effectiveness of the lesson.

Key word: *Teaching system, teacher and student, education, skill, knowledge, person, science, society, norm, ethics.*

Introduction: To provide students with sufficient knowledge, skills and abilities, according to the requirements of the State Education Standard, the goal should be taken into account by the head of the class. Because of fulfilling the requirements of DTS, increasing the creative initiative of students, the development of independent thinking skills in students will be strengthened. The educational process, as the core of the pedagogical process, embodies the unity of self-education, in addition, social experience. Education in the educational process is mainly manifested in the form of teaching. The teacher encourages schoolchildren to actively perceive new knowledge and apply it. Part of the research: One of the important problems facing the science of pedagogy today is the problem of teacher and pedagogical working conditions. Because all pedagogical ideas are embodied in the teacher, and these ideas are implemented and implemented through his activities. At the heart of the multifaceted and complex activity of a teacher, it is as important as educating the young generation

to be polite and moral, arming them with knowledge. The implementation of these depends on the various activities of the teacher: teaching children, being able to organize and conduct educational activities outside of school and the classroom, conducting pedagogical propaganda among parents, etc. All this requires the teacher to have deep knowledge, to love his field and children. School management and the community play a major role in the professional development of a teacher. It is the duty of the school management to attach experienced teachers to young teachers, monitor their lessons, and involve them in the work of method integration. In the school, great importance is attached to the teacher's work on himself, constantly improving his scientific-theoretical and methodical knowledge. The teacher, while gradually mastering his profession, promotes pedagogical knowledge among parents. The process of entering the teaching profession and acquiring pedagogical skills depends on whether he is able to enter the team of schoolteachers and find his place in it. Not turning away from the support of the team, not getting discouraged when faced with difficulties, being able to see one's own mistakes and try to eliminate them is a sign of his formation as a teacher.

At the same time, trying to educate yourself and work tirelessly on yourself is an integral part of professional qualities.

The regulation "On the attestation of teaching staff of public educational institutions of the Republic of Uzbekistan" was developed and this regulation was approved by the decision of the Cabinet of Ministers on August 12, 1993. Attestation allows teachers and other pedagogical staff to receive a salary according to the result of their work, and guarantees that if a pedagogue works well in the process of education and training, his work will not go unnoticed. The educational requirements for the lesson are to determine the educational possibilities of the educational material, the activity in the lesson, the formation and setting of educational goals that can be clearly achieved, the definition of educational issues that naturally arise from the goals and content of educational work, educating students in universal human values, forming vital qualities (diligence, orderliness, responsibility, discipline, independence, ability

to do work, ability, attentiveness, honesty, etc.) implementation, cooperation with students and their success. Developmental requirements that are always implemented in all lessons include positive initiative and qualities of students' learning activities, interest, creative initiative and activity, formation and development, study of the level of students' perceptive abilities, consideration, and close development. Designing the zone, organizing educational activities at the level of excellence, encouraging new changes in their development, anticipating leaps in the intellectual, emotional, and social development of students, taking into account the beginning changes includes operational restructuring of training.

Conclusion: Nowadays, knowledge, understanding, application, analysis, synthesis, evaluation of teacher's pedagogical skills are important categories of education. In addition, teaching is an activity that organizes in a planned and systematic way in order to make social behavior a permanent form. The mind of the students - the taught knowledge is the level of spiritual understanding activity based on the understanding of life and worldly reality through their perception, intelligence. Students should complete the tasks, read and additionally read newspaper guides on the subject. Arastu, who is considered our famous thinker: "You know that a person who is engaged in education and training cannot give education and training to others if he himself is uneducated and uneducated." A person with good character cannot start others to do naughty and dirty things.

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